

Determination of Gallium in Rocks and Minerals by Solvent Extraction and Atomic Absorption Spectrometry

N. K. ROY

Central Chemical Laboratory, Geological Survey of India, 15 A/B, Kyd Street, Calcutta-700 016

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The abundance of gallium in geological samples is about 10–25 ppm. At such a low level no method is suitable for direct determination of Ga. Flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS) technique is not sensitive enough to be applicable directly to the determination of Ga in geological samples. Preconcentration is generally required before it is determined by FAAS. Amongst the preconcentration techniques, solvent extraction has been extensively used for separation of trace elements. Several authors^{1–3} reported determination of gallium in geological samples by applying solvent extraction followed by FAAS measurement. However, these methods are either time-consuming or the sensitivity is reduced because of back-extraction and measurement in aqueous medium. Graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GFAAS) technique also suffers from severe matrix problem⁴. In this communication, a simple solvent extraction-cum-FAAS method is described. The method has been applied to several international standard samples and the results are compared.

Results and Discussion

Gallium is completely extracted from 7 N HCl⁵. Below this acid concentration the extraction is either incomplete or irregular. No other element except Fe^{III} is likely to be extracted at this acid concentration. Fe^{III} ion is reduced to Fe^{II} by ascorbic acid and hence its extraction is completely arrested. The proposed method has been applied to a number of international standard samples (Table 1). Relative standard deviation measured with sample JA-1 was

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Ga BY SOLVENT EXTRACTION-AAS

Sample	Ga(ppm)	
	Found	Reported
JR-1. Rhyolite	17.0	17.6 ^a
JA-1. Andesite	17.5	17.3 ^a
JGb-1. Gabbro	18.6	18.9 ^a
GSP-1. Granodiorite	22.2	22.0 ^b
CRPG. Bauxite, BXN	85	68–115 ^c
GSI. Bauxite, BUX-24	107	105 ^c

^aRef. 6. ^bRef. 7. ^cRef. 3.

found to be 5%. The method is practically free from interferences and easy to perform. Generally 1 g rock sample is taken for determination of gallium. However, a smaller amount (0.25 g) is sufficient in case of bauxite sample. Both acid decomposition and alkali fusion methods are equally effective. Alkali fusion method is preferred in case of bauxite sample.

Experimental

A Perkin-Elmer 300 atomic absorption instrument fitted with PE hollow cathode lamp was used for FAAS measurement done at 278.6 nm line using air-acetylene flame and standard operating conditions.

Standard Ga solution (100 µg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving gallium oxide (Spec pure) in dilute HCl; further dilutions were made as necessary before use. Trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO)-methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) reagent was prepared by dissolving TOPO (2 g) in MIBK (100 ml). All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Acid decomposition (rock sample): Finely powdered rock sample (1 g) was treated with perchloric acid (5 ml) and HF (10 ml) and the mixture was heated on a hot-plate for ~2 h, then evaporated to incipient dryness. A second such operation was performed with perchloric acid (2 ml) and HF (5 ml). The mass was then dissolved in 7 N HCl (10 ml) and reserved for liquid-liquid extraction.

Alkali fusion (bauxite sample): The sample (0.25 g) was fused with NaOH (5 g) in nickel crucible for 20 min. The cooled mass was then dissolved in 7 N HCl and reserved for the solvent extraction step.

Liquid-liquid extraction and flame AAS measurement: The test solution was diluted to 50 ml with 7 N HCl. Ascorbic acid (1 g) was then added to it and shaken with TOPO-MIBK mixture (5 ml) for 2 min. The separated organic phase was received in a dry test tube containing 1 g anhydrous sodium sulphate and the supernate was used for FAAS measurement. Calibration solutions containing 5–25 µg of Ga were prepared following the above extraction method.

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